

MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR BIO-INSPIRED SYSTEMS ALLOWING AUTONOMIC RESPONSE

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Abstract

The area of multifunctional structures has become prominent in the last few years with a number of definitions and concepts being put forth. The most popular definition is a structure that has the ability to perform multiple tasks through judicious combinations of structural integrity with specific functional properties dictated by the system requirements. Some researchers take a rather pragmatic view of multifunctional design by starting with a conventional composite and incorporating the additional layers with specific functionality. Others try to emulate biological systems, in which jointed frameworks and complex materials impart active functionality at multiple length scales. It is hoped that individual material elements are concurrently participating in distinct, beneficial physical processes thereby delivering truly dramatic improvements in system-level efficiency instead of incremental improvements. Among various visionary contexts for developing a new generation of multifunctional structures, the most revolutionary one appears to be “autonomic” systems that can sense, diagnose and respond to external stimuli with minimal intervention. One prominent example of autonomic response has been “self-healing” polymers and composites that mimic the autonomic repair process of biological systems in response to damage. Ever since this novel concept was demonstrated barely twelve years ago, the worldwide support has allowed focusing extensive research efforts to the subject of autonomic structures in ever-expanding scope. For instance, the multidisciplinary research efforts have established the concepts of “micro-vascular composites for self-cooling or autonomic thermal management,” “neurological system inspired network for self-sensing and actuation,” “self-powered systems with structurally integrated energy harvesting and storage capabilities,” etc. Such structures would be able to attain each of specific functionalities, adapt to new situations, and perhaps reconfigure them to respond to a perceived threat or change of environment. Dramatic improvement in system-level efficiency is expected to be achieved not only by designing multifunctional load-bearing structures with integrated functional properties but also by developing multifunctional composite materials that inherently possess the capacity to simultaneously meet the requirements for specific functionality as well as mechanical load carrying capability. Our research vision is additionally inspired by the way in which nature uses stimuli-responsive biomolecules to incorporate autonomic behavior in cellular systems. Noting the ability of cellular systems to communicate via charge and mass transport at cellular interfaces, the researchers try to create a new class of material systems that incorporate one or more internal networks of biomolecules whose transport properties can be controlled by external stimuli. Each of the cited examples points the values of a truly autonomic system capable of multiple functions to survive its operating condition and environment for longer periods of time than the traditional structures can endure.